

Neurobiological Origins and Treatment of ADHD in Youth

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ABSTRACT

Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a prevalent neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. Symptoms such as these commonly surface during early stages of youth or adolescence, and frequently persist into adulthood. This literature review integrates current research on the complex roots of ADHD, surrounding neurological, genetic, and environmental components. Understanding these roots is critical for advancing treatment strategies, as it allows for more targeted and effective interventions that address the underlying mechanisms of ADHD. It highlights how these aspects contribute to abnormalities in typical brain development, particularly in areas related to inhibition, attention, and reward processing. Key neurological irregularities, including decreased prefrontal cortex volume, impaired connectivity between the prefrontal cortex and striatum, and reduced amygdala and hippocampal volumes, are examined to clarify their roles in the disorder's symptoms. Treatments for ADHD include both pharmacological options, such as stimulants and non-stimulants, and non-pharmacological alternatives, like cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), neurofeedback, and other interventions are discussed in detail.

Keywords: *ADHD, neurodevelopmental, behavior, adolescence, brain connectivity, inattention, hyperactivity.*

1. Introduction

Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a common neurodevelopmental psychiatric disorder, with symptoms beginning in childhood. The etiology of ADHD is thought to be attributed to a variety of different factors including environmental, genetic, and neurological abnormalities (Akutagava-Martins et al., 2016). The primary symptoms of ADHD include inattentiveness, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, often joined by other secondary problems. These symptoms have been linked to difficulty socializing, lower self esteem, weak academic performance, and impulsive behavior (Faraone & Radonjić, 2023). Although symptoms can improve, and sometimes remit completely, most ADHD symptoms continue throughout adulthood for a majority of patients (Biederman, 1998). ADHD has become a widespread diagnosis throughout the United States, with approximately 8% of children between the ages of four to 17 experiencing ADHD (Froehlich & Brinkman, 2018), with the number being about 7.6% for children globally (Salari et al., 2023). In children younger than four years old, it is difficult to provide a reliable diagnosis because typical behavior at this age may be mistaken for symptoms of ADHD, such as tantrums or restlessness (Christner et al., 2013).

ADHD is a difficult disorder to diagnose because its symptoms can resemble those of other psychological disorders. Anxiety, for example, has symptoms similar to ADHD such as fidgeting. Therefore, the diagnostic criteria physicians should follow to correctly diagnose ADHD is specific. The diagnostic criteria for ADHD based on the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM), 5th edition, includes experiencing consistent behaviors that limit functioning or development, and align with inattention, hyperactivity and/or impulsivity (American Psychiatric Association (APA), 2013). Using the DSM criteria to diagnose ADHD is important because it ensures accuracy and distinguishes ADHD from similar disorders. Some indicators for inattention include: overlooking details or making errors during tasks such as homework, difficulty remaining focused during activities that require prolonged engagement, struggles to

listen when spoken to, failure to complete assignments or becoming easily distracted while doing them, having trouble organizing tasks and activities, reluctance to participate in activities, losing necessary items for said activities, being easily distracted by outside thoughts or unrelated stimuli, and forgetting to do daily tasks. Some patients may show hyperactivity along with inattention, while others may experience hyperactivity without inattention. In children, this can appear as fidgeting, difficulty sitting still, running or climbing in inappropriate situations, struggling with quiet activities, talking excessively, interrupting others, and speaking impulsively before a question is fully asked. In adults, hyperactivity may manifest as restlessness, constant movement (such as tapping or shifting positions), an inability to relax, excessive talking, interrupting conversations, impulsively making decisions, and feeling the need to stay constantly busy. It is important to note that a patient may not experience all of these symptoms, and in individuals over the age of 17, these symptoms may appear in more subtle forms, such as the ones mentioned previously. However, an ADHD diagnosis requires that a patient has experienced at least six of these symptoms regularly over a span of six months. Additionally, patients must have also expressed inattentiveness or hyperactive-impulsive behaviors before the age of twelve, and have presented these symptoms in at least two different environments (e.g., at home, school, work). It must also be taken into account whether the patient has been or could be diagnosed with a psychotic disorder (e.g., schizophrenia) or other mental disorders (e.g., anxiety disorder, bipolar disorder, dissociative disorder), as these symptoms could be features of a different psychological disorder, and may not be ADHD (APA, 2013).

Although treatments for ADHD are still being explored, there are many options that are currently recommended. Pharmacological treatments, such as stimulants, non-stimulants, and other approved drugs, have been shown to be most effective for symptoms of ADHD (Catala-Lopez et al., 2015). There are also non-pharmacological interventions that include psychological treatments, devices, and alternative methods including supplements and dietary interventions (Catala-Lopez et al., 2017; Bader & Adesman, 2012). Some psychological interventions include, but are not limited to, parent training, classroom intervention, neurofeedback, and cognitive behavioral therapy.

2. Discussion

2.1 Typical Brain Development

There are a number of cognitive skills developed throughout childhood that are implicated in the development of ADHD. Childhood is a period marked by significant neurodevelopmental changes in inhibition, sustaining attention, reward processing, and executive functioning behaviors. During these years, a number of skills are developed that are crucial in life. The first two to three years of age are categorized by rapid growth and development of parts of the brain that are subject to cognitive function (Gilmore et al., 2018).

Inhibition is the ability to stop oneself from doing something voluntarily or involuntarily. More specifically, it is the capacity to stop an inappropriate gesture from being executed. Studies have shown that inhibition is mostly developed during early stages of childhood, and develops rapidly throughout those years (Petersen et al., 2016). Inhibition control is held in the prefrontal cortex, although many regions are involved in executing and obtaining inhibition tasks (Munakata et al., 2011). The prefrontal cortex undergoes substantial development during early childhood, which includes the growth of the dendrites, reduction of the synaptic and neuronal density, and growth of white matter volume. Due to these changes, neural networks are able to create responses for cognitive and executive functions (Uytun, 2018) related to inhibitory control.

Another important cognitive function is attention, or the concentration or action of focusing a task or an aspect that contains information. Attention develops throughout childhood, mainly during school-age, and is one of the most important cognitive functions in humans (Suades-González et al., 2017). By age three, parents should be able to answer questions about their children's behavior regarding how they respond to attention-driven tasks (Posner et al., 2014). Through ages five to nine, attention is rapidly developing and slowly ventures into an ongoing stage with little change (Betts et al., 2006).

Past research suggests that there are three main networks related to attention. These include the alerting network, the executive network, and the orienting network. Each of these is made out of multiple neuronal networks (Posner & Petersen, 1990). A study conducted using an attention network test (ANT) and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) found that the right temporal parietal junction showed significant activation in the alerting system. Within the alerting system there was also fronto-parietal cortical activity along with the thalamus, anterior

intraparietal activity, inferior parietal, frontal activity, and the superior colliculus. In the executive network, anterior cingulate and right and left frontal areas were active, along with the fusiform gyrus. In the orienting network, the study found that the left and right superior parietal lobe was activated (Fan et al., 2005). Multiple studies have shown that the superior parietal lobe, visual association cortex, left precentral gyrus, supplementary motor area, anterior cingulate cortex, visual association cortex, lateral prefrontal cortex, thalamus, and caudate were activated during attention related tasks (Saito et al., 2022). Attention engages a complex network of regions and circuits throughout the brain.

Reward processing implements behavior in our daily life and can provide positive (e.g., fulfilling hunger and thirst) or negative outcomes (e.g., alcohol and drug use). During adolescence, many necessary neural centers for reward processing and goal-orientation (e.g., frontal corticobasal ganglia networks) are still developing. As a result, adolescents frequently make risky decisions, not being fully aware of what the outcomes may be (Fareri et al., 2008). Studies have shown that most of the brain (about 90-95%) is usually developed around the ages of five to six (Casey et al., 2000). After this period, there is little change regarding the cerebellar volume, although it has been shown that there are changes with the development of cortical gray and white matter, along with subcortical structure changes within reward circuitry (Caviness et al., 1996).

2.2 Neurobiology of ADHD

There is not a primary cause of ADHD and the etiology of the disorder is still being researched today. This is because ADHD is likely caused by a variety of factors and does not have a single distinct origin or cause (Curatolo et al., 2010). It has been studied that genetics and environmental risk factors interact and together have the ability to trigger symptoms of the disorder or increase the probability of having ADHD (Sonuga-Barke & Halperin, 2010). However, as the disorder is neurodevelopmental, the most common “cause” of ADHD is attributed to altered neurobiological structure and functioning of the brain.

2.3 Genetic Findings

The relationship between genetics and ADHD is still being explored and is not fully understood (Curatolo et al., 2010). Gene studies done with ADHD have found multiple genes

that are associated with disorder, supporting a role of genes with the codings DRD4, DRD5, SLC6A3, SNAP-25, and HTR1B (Faraone et al., 2005). There have also been reports of potential linkage between alleles for ADHD and certain chromosomes (Ogdie et al., 2004), but genome-wide studies have not shown significant associations for this to be fully approved as a possible cause for ADHD (Franke et al., 2010). There is a connection between ADHD and genes that regulate dopamine, noradrenaline, and serotonin (Bralten et al., 2013). This may be due to the correlation between these neurotransmitters and reward processing, which is something ADHD patients sometimes struggle with. Siblings and parents of children with ADHD are at a 5-10% higher risk of developing the disorder compared to those who don't have someone with ADHD in their family (Biederman et al., 1990; Biederman et al., 1992). An example of this could be seen in twin studies, where a combination of results from 20 twin studies done on ADHD, discovered a mean of 76% heritability of the disorder (Faraone et al., 2005).

2.4 Structural Differences

2.4.1 Subcortical Structures

Significant differences in brain structure have been observed in individuals with ADHD relative to those without the disorder. Studies using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have found that patients with ADHD have considerably smaller volumes in certain subcortical structures (e.g., accumbens, amygdala, caudate, hippocampus, and putamen) and intracranial volume (Hoogman et al., 2017). Subcortical regions of the brain such as these play a pivotal role in cognitive, affective, and social functions, which could explain why patients with ADHD struggle with tasks that require these types of functions. Decreased volume of the amygdala could explain why many patients with ADHD have problems with regulating their emotions (Faraone et al., 2019). In this study, the authors found that brain volume changed between different age groups, and they explained that patients with ADHD showed delayed brain maturation, specifically in subcortical areas (Faraone et al., 2019).

A comprehensive review of studies using volumetric region-of-interest (ROI) analysis, which evaluates specific brain region volumes, examined total brain volume in the basal ganglia, amygdala, hippocampus, and cerebellar regions. This analysis revealed significant volume reduction in the cerebellar vermis (Valera et al., 2007). In individuals with ADHD, decreases in volume have been noted in total cerebral volume, the prefrontal cortex, the basal ganglia

(specifically, the striatum), the dorsal anterior cingulate cortex, the corpus callosum, and the cerebellum (Emond et al., 2008).

2.4.2 Cortical Regions

It has also been observed that children with ADHD lack cortical surface area as well as decreased cortical thickness in fusiform, parahippocampal, precentral gyrus, and temporal lobe when compared to children without ADHD. These differences were only seen in children (ages 4-9), and not in adolescents and adults (Hoogman et al., 2019). Children with ADHD have also shown changes regarding cortical folding. A study done with 21 children with ADHD, and a control group of 35 typically developing children, revealed that children with ADHD showed a significant decrease in cortical folding bilaterally (Wolosin et al., 2009). Overall, many studies would imply that the brains of children with ADHD are significantly smaller in relation to unaffected children (Curatolo et al., 2010).

2.4.3 Regional and Connectivity Differences

Alongside structural differences, researchers have observed many differences in regional activation and functional connectivity in children with ADHD using various types of brain scans including FMRI, MRI, PET scans.

2.5 Reward processing in children with ADHD

Children with ADHD can experience challenges with reward processing, as they may show unconventional behavioral responses to reward. One of the characteristics of ADHD is impulsivity, which can cause people with ADHD to pick smaller, more immediate rewards over delayed, more important ones.

It has been found that children with ADHD have distinct regional and connectivity differences within the reward system compared to children without the disorder. A study using a child-friendly version of the monetary incentive delay (MID) task recruited boys between the ages of 8-12 years. Ultimately, data was collected from 76 of the participants, 27 being typically developing children, 24 children with ADHD, and 25 children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) as well as ADHD symptoms. They revealed that children with ADHD symptoms exhibited decreased activity in the ventral striatum, and that the degree of ADHD symptoms did

not affect the activity within the ventral striatum (Van Hulst et al., 2017). Another study using the MID task concluded that patients with ADHD presented less connectivity between the salience network and the executive control network when compared to the control group. It was discovered that control participants demonstrated stronger functional connectivity in comparison to participants with ADHD (von Rhein et al., 2017). On the contrary, one study found opposing results, concluding that they did not observe notable ADHD-related differences in functional connectivity of the salience network (Oldehinkel et al., 2016). Both studies used different methods and sample sizes to gather information, which may explain the contradictory findings.

2.6 Working memory in children with ADHD

Working memory impairments are not seen in every case of ADHD, however some deficits are commonly observed in people with ADHD. Working memory capacity is often measured by asking individuals to complete tasks that require holding or remembering information over a certain period of time. One study tested working memory in adolescents with ADHD by asking the participants to recall three to four objects in forward to backward order during fMRI scans. The study analyzed results from 50 ADHD participants and 82 participants that were a part of the control group. The ADHD group exhibited hypoactivation in the right striatum, the right cerebellum, and the left occipital gyrus in comparison to the control group during higher working memory loads and greater complexity of tasks. A relationship was also measured between brain activity and cognitive load of a task or the complexity of a stimulus. The study found a relationship between ADHD and load in the striatum, and between ADHD and complexity in the right cerebellum and the left occipital gyrus (Mukherjee et al., 2021). Another study that explored working memory in children with ADHD found that children with ADHD presented significantly decreased activation levels in regions involved in working memory processes. This included the inferior parietal areas, caudate nucleus, cerebellum, and the brainstem nuclei. The study's findings were found using fMRI scans while the children participated in a N-back task that involved pressing a button when a certain number was displayed (Massat et al., 2012).

2.7 Environmental and external factors

Though ADHD has a strong genetic predisposition, every individual who is at risk of developing ADHD does not go on to develop the disorder. It has been discussed that environmental factors can play a role in the ultimate development of the disorder.

Previous studies have shown that certain prenatal activities have been linked to ADHD, such as maternal stress during pregnancy (Talge et al., 2007), exposure to alcohol, drugs, tobacco, and other environmental toxins (Pineda et al., 2007), as well as low birth weight (Strang-Karlsson et al., 2008). These are some examples of environmental risk factors that have been found to potentially be associated with ADHD, as there are more that are still being researched. It's important to note that experiencing these events does not guarantee a diagnosis of ADHD, rather they likely interact with existing genetic vulnerabilities.

2.8 Treatments for ADHD

There is no ultimate cure for ADHD that has been discovered yet, however there are many treatment options that can be recommended to people with ADHD, with pharmacological interventions recommended as the first line treatment for the disorder. There are other alternatives including, but not limited to, non-pharmacological interventions such as behavioral therapies, cognitive training, psychoeducation, and others that are still being researched today (Nazarova et al., 2022).

2.8.1 Pharmacological treatments

The first treatment for ADHD most commonly recommended by physicians is the use of stimulant drugs. This treatment recommendation is supported by research that suggests stimulants are effective in reducing symptoms of ADHD (Barbaresi et al., 2007). Psychostimulants that include methylphenidate, dextroamphetamine, and mixed amphetamine salts such as dextroamphetamine/amphetamine (Adderall) seem to be the most effective and safe option (Wolraich et al., 2019). In addition to helping major symptoms, stimulants also improve social behavior (Hinshaw, 1991), authority, parent, and peer interactions (Granger et al., 1996), and academic performance (Carlson et al., 1992). Stimulants can come in long-acting and short-acting formulas, both having advantages. Short-acting stimulants allow patients to have more flexibility with regards to taking the medication, while long-acting formulations have been associated with greater adherence to the medication (Hodgkins et al., 2012). Methylphenidate is

one of the more common psychostimulants used to treat ADHD. Methylphenidate works by increasing the levels of the neurotransmitters dopamine and norepinephrine. Methylphenidate has shown to decrease ADHD symptoms in children and increase quality of life (Cortese et al., 2018). A study done with 40 children, ages 6-12, used methylphenidate and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) on 20 of the children, and methylphenidate with a placebo on the second group. They discovered that the first group of children experienced a greater reduction in the severity of their symptoms in comparison with the second group (Moghaddam et al., 2017). Another study found that methylphenidate significantly reduced ADHD symptoms, both with folic acid, and with a placebo as a replacement of the folic acid (Ghanizadeh et al., 2013).

There are many factors that should be considered when deciding if stimulants are the right path for a patient with ADHD. Stimulants provide patients with faster results, and don't require much effort or time to be invested into them. Stimulants are more accessible in comparison to less popular methods of treatment, as doctors are able to prescribe them. However, depending on the patient, stimulants can potentially become addictive and present a higher likelihood of drug abuse than some other treatments. Patients should also consider potential side effects and risks that may come along with said stimulant.

Non-stimulants are another approach used to treat ADHD. They differ from stimulants in that they do not directly target dopamine and norepinephrine neurotransmitters. Some non-stimulants include atomoxetine, clonidine, and guanfacine. Atomoxetine is the first non-stimulant to be approved by the FDA, and has shown to improve symptoms of ADHD. In a study using 584 patients with ADHD, atomoxetine provided better results regarding severity of ADHD symptoms and quality of life in comparison to a placebo drug (Durell et al., 2013).

There is also the possibility of combining certain pharmacological medications. A study conducted using 929 patients with an ADHD diagnosis used both atomoxetine and methylphenidate as treatment. The participants of the study were either treated using only atomoxetine, only methylphenidate, both atomoxetine and methylphenidate but separately used, or both with combined use. The study found that the combined method using the stimulant and the non-stimulant had significant long-term effects, and exceeded mono-pharmacy results (Bahn & Seo, 2021).

2.8.2 Neurofeedback

Although medication can be effective for some, alternative procedures can enhance the lives of many with this disorder. Neurofeedback is a type of therapy that monitors brain activity to provide feedback to the individual. It is a non-pharmacological and non-invasive approach that has shown notable results without side effects (Hammond & Kirk, 2007). The goal is to help individuals learn to control brain function and improve cognitive performance (Vernon, 2005). Neurofeedback works by placing small sensors onto the patient's scalp to measure brain waves. These sensors connect to a computer to help analyze brain electrical activity. After the computer analyzes the brain waves, it sends feedback such as sounds, visual displays or even types of sensation. When the brain provides positive activity, the computer will respond with positive feedback, as a way of encouraging the brain to repeat the action. Neurofeedback is a relatively new approach to ADHD that is still being researched. Neurofeedback has shown to improve ADHD symptoms and improve attention and reaction times in children (Bakhshayesh et al., 2011). Another study also found similar results, concluding that children who completed 40, 45 minute-long sessions over the course of five months, showed improvements in ADHD symptoms and sustained improvements six months after the intervention was complete (Steiner et al., 2014). Neurofeedback has shown to provide long-lasting results that can potentially increase overtime, rather than medications, which in certain situations can diminish over time (Van Doren et al., 2019).

It is important to mention that neurofeedback may not be as accessible as pharmacological treatments, especially for people who live in remote areas. For many, medication is easier to obtain through the help of a physician, while neurofeedback may be more unattainable to certain families. The price of most medication is also covered by insurance, or may come out to be cheaper than the cost of neurofeedback sessions, which are not always covered under insurance. Additionally, neurofeedback is a lengthy process that requires much time and effort, and results are not as quick to show in comparison to stimulants and non-stimulants.

2.8.3 Cognitive Behavioral Therapy

Along with medication, behavioral therapies can improve and reduce the severity of ADHD symptoms. The combination of cognitive therapy and drug therapy has shown significant efforts that are able to help patients with the disorder. An example of one of these therapies is

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). CBT is a psychotherapy that focuses on changing negative behaviors using positive, rewarding activities and challenging unhelpful thought patterns. It can also include exposing individuals to their fears in order to help with phobias or anxiety. Many behavioral therapies, including CBT, are used together with medication to provide the best results. One study used 45 children ages 7-13 that had ADHD to observe the effects of CBT. Adolescents were split into groups of 15, one group being the control group, one receiving only CBT, and the other receiving combined therapy or CBT and a drug. The study concluded that the combined therapy was more effective in reducing ADHD symptoms than drug therapy alone. However, CBT alone and combined therapy provided similar results, meaning that one did not surpass the other (Aghaee & Tarkhan, 2017). Another study that used CBT found different results, suggesting that combined therapy did not outperform drug therapy (Coelho et al., 2017). Results may vary based on what drug is used, the dose used, the technique used within the therapy, and the amount of sessions and/or length of the therapy, as well as other factors.

Similarly to neurofeedback, CBT may not be available to certain ADHD patients when considering cost, insurance, and accessibility. It also requires more time and effort than drugs, and potential results may not be visible as quickly as medications offer.

2.8.4 Further Alternative Treatments

School-age children with ADHD commonly display disobedient and aggressive behaviors in addition to the disorder's core symptoms. Such behaviors can lead to academic struggles, frustrated parents, isolation, and self-esteem issues (Young & Myanathi Amarasinghe, 2010). Sometimes, stimulants are not able to solve this problem, or a child may be too young for a certain type of medical drug. Possible treatments for families who wish to improve such symptoms should look into parent training. Parent training is a family of treatment programs which aim to teach parents positive and supportive methods for improving their child's behavior. This can include taking upon new disciplinary techniques, and using more beneficial and less negative forms of punishment for bad behavior (Antshel & Barkley, 2008). Parent training is seen as an efficacious intervention for behavioral symptoms by many parents. A study done on 164 pre-school children ages 3-4, using parent training concluded that after a year, parents saw improvements in their children's behaviors. This claim however was not supported by the teacher ratings that were included in the study (Abikoff et al., 2015). Some studies state that

parent training outcomes can provide a moderate effect, but effects can decrease at follow-ups (Lee et al., 2012).

Improvements and changes in diet have also shown to have credible outcomes on children with ADHD. One diet in particular, by the name of the DASH diet (Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension) showed great improvement in behavioral and emotional symptoms for ADHD in a twelve week study done with children ages 6-12. The DASH diet consists of nutrient-rich foods that are low in sodium, saturated fat, and added sugars. It focuses on fruits, vegetables, whole grains, lean protein, dairy, and healthy fats such as nuts. This study showed that adolescents who were a part of the DASH diet group showed substantial reductions in attention and concentration issues, hyperactivity, conduct problems, and peer relationship problems. They also showed consistent reports from parents, teachers, and other professionals (Khoshbakht et al., 2021). However, dietary interventions do not always show considerable improvements, depending on the person and the diet that is being recommended for them. This was seen in a study done by Ghanizadeh and Haddad (2015), where the dietary group did not reveal significant differences when compared to the control group.

Although there is no cure for ADHD, there are many different treatment options that are open to patients. New remedies and treatment options are being further researched, showing success for many people. When deciding what intervention can be right for a patient, it is important to consider all factors and consequences that surround a treatment, which should be discussed with a physician.

2.9 Future Directions

Researchers should further investigate the structural and functional differences in the brains of individuals with ADHD, so that a better understanding could be reached on the neurobiology of ADHD. This could help identify biomarkers to target in treatment studies and provide a more objective diagnosis. Further developed research should be conducted on the impact and long-term outcome of different treatments. This would truly show how effective certain treatments are, and provide more reliable comparisons of different interventions. It could be helpful to follow children with ADHD to see if their brains change or develop.

Bigger and more diverse population sizes must be considered for treatment studies so that treatments can be better known and researched more thoroughly. Physicians should be more

thorough and provide more in-depth evaluations when trying to diagnose a child with ADHD so that their diagnosis can be more precise and accurate. Physicians should also provide additional follow-ups for patients who have been diagnosed with ADHD.

3. Conclusion

ADHD is a complex disorder that affects much of the population today, ranging from adults to children. It is categorized by symptoms of impulsivity, inattention, and hyperactivity which impact social, attentional and academic performance. Its neurobiology lies within structural differences as well as genetic findings and sometimes environmental factors. Although there is no official cure for ADHD, different treatment options are available including stimulants, non-stimulants, therapies, and more which are still being researched today.

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